

Hurdles in Progression of Knowledge and its Global Impact

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Abstract

Though since beginning Human beings were in quest for learning but over period of time its means mode and medium have been changing with evolution of varying impact of knowledge on life and living standard. In this modern era where everywhere there is a possibility to be watched for having IT gadgets publishing knowledge and its dispersion have acquired different modes differently acknowledged in academic circles varying from region to region and outcome is there has been an impact of being religiously and regionally biased politically influenced power driven selection on accessibility and transmission of knowledge including its propagation and its translation into technology. This prevailing trend has adversely effected the reproducibility of the a considerable amount of work whereas its authenticity and originality have become doubtful, as investigations on most of the queries have been in progress without referring and critical analysis of published work partly for the classification of journals on different basis, many are considered bogus hence are not referred and the other reason is the work published has limited access. Publishing an original novel piece of work in limited globally acknowledged Journals technically should not affect the credibility in terms of recognition of work but in real world of Science it never happens. Getting through peer review process for publishing any novel original work by struggling globally unknown researchers practically becomes very difficult because of conflict of interest that exist among established groups of Scientists. The earlier work by Rab, FA covered different aspect of flaws prevailing in profession of teaching and research in area of higher education. This piece of work is written revealing, how flaws prevailing in existing system of teaching and research have been the hindrance in reporting one of the most novel findings of this era in area of Molecular Biology explored using out of box thinking based smart approach explored in a very short time, its dispersion and acknowledgement globally for doing needful by academicians researchers health experts working in medical and allied fields and also by business professionals catering the need of Global Community, situation in developing countries having poor infra structures of institutes is even more intensely challenging.

Keywords: Research publication; Novel findings; Epigenetics illnesses; Formats of reporting higher education policy; Business policy; Globally integrated quality standards

Evolution of Learning means Mode and Media

Knowledge is a never ending quest of knowing and research is a mean of its progression. Any investigation that is planned to study any problem on knowledge is done after referring the WHOLE work published in that said area. The more intense the literature review, more deepen the study is expected to be however in area of research the main thing is nothing is final and absolute and with arriving to an answer there arises queries in parallel. In olden rather golden days, scholar used to do research mainly because they had quest for knowledge, however those days doing research was not an established profession and the continuation of career in research used not to be dependent on continuation of funding, number of publications and registration of patents hence research or books published used to be globally accepted and respected for their authenticity.

There was lesser impact on any study for being regionally confined or religiously biased. Multi-religious seminars catering debates on different issues including controversial ones also used to be held in routine. Generally people used to have comparatively more respect and tolerance for scholars and even for their controversial notions however the professional competition among different scholars has been there since beginning but they used to adhere to practices for good ethics and high moral values in more profound manners.

As already mentioned earlier as well the methodology to proceed with any investigative study is to review whole published work critically and independently before planning for future study. Nothing is absolute fact is another established fact for so far what s established in knowledge as most of the time earlier established findings are modified or even discarded in future conducted study s conclusions. In simple words the research is a process of learning and unlearning and the findings are supposed to be globally accepted.

Since the practice of research emerged as a profession and with it got associated the name fame money and authority,

there appeared a trend of greed and being regionally and religiously biased approach that MUST be discouraged GLOBALLY as nothing else more than these practices have damaged the authenticity of research content hence it has become difficult to differentiate between fair and fake [1,2]. Only with having deep insight on knowledge, it is possible to get well equipped to judge the authenticity of published work. Since research and teaching have emerged as profession these days the prerequisite to continue profession in it at higher education level is to have conferred PhD, a research degree awarded after doing some original reproducible work done in the given area on having published the work in a recognized journal the trend to steal research ideas has increased [1].

In olden days, research used to be less technology based. People used to type their work on type writer unlike these days where computer is a quick mean of saving the work get connected with other researchers and get access to their work. Different professional forums e.g. linkedin and researchgate etc emerged over a period of time where professionals get themselves registered to be part of global community of respective professions and share their progression in career globally while keeping an eye on future opportunities both in terms of career and emerging trends in knowledge and technology.

With having involvement of technology in research, there appeared a need of sustainable flow of finance in this field, that is a key hindrance to sustain authenticity and reproducibility of research work, generally generated having compromised originality and reproducibility, mainly for lacking infrastructure of institutes and their policies having serious flaws mainly because they are designed to serve regional demand rather often the personal interests e.g. individuals are better serve than addressing the problem [1,2]. As already stated earlier as well publishing an original novel piece of work in limited globally acknowledged Journals technically should not affect the credibility in terms of recognition of work but these days in real world of Science it never happens. Getting through peer review process for publishing any novel original work by struggling globally unknown researchers practically becomes very difficult because of conflict of interest that exist among established groups of Scientists. There has been an increasing trend of having an impact of being religiously and regionally biased politically influenced power driven selection on accessibility and transmission of knowledge including its propagation and its translation into technology. This problem is more intense in developing part of world. Since they rely more for Human Development Resources on their own poorly developed infrastructure, there is continuous ongoing depletion of trained manpower on global standard in area of Higher Education and Research. There is a general emphasis of establishing high technology based laboratories in developing countries as compared of doing brilliant science manually using minimal equipments e.g. less technology dependency a skill that most of the Universities in United Kingdom including University of Nottingham focus upon hence the cost of doing research is much higher in technology driven laboratories than needed at such places whereas the work requires more input of technologists than the researcher conducting the study adding

the provision of error while diminishing the reproducibility particularly in Biological Sciences.

Generally Research Authority Bodies design policies and provide guidelines for research activity whereas mostly in developing countries focus is on the requirement of individuals rather than institutes development at global standard. Making the condition for having a PhD degree a must for progression of career at University level has immensely damaged the research standard. Acquiring research training is not necessarily be a compatible learning activity as per traits of any individual e.g. a good cook is not necessarily be a good thinker and investigator, the basic traits for doing research, for lacking them but since if individuals somehow happen to come into the profession of research and teaching, acquiring PhD and doing research is a MUST for them. Locally published journals recognized by research authorities of respective countries are an easier mean of publishing such work that does not necessarily meet the internationally recognized criterion of conducting research study but is good enough for having career progression in field of Teaching and Research at the same place. Since not all the journals are recognized by regional research authorities, hence a huge and reasonably valuable research content is left out from being referred while planning any research study or analyzing it, making research considerably regionally and religiously biased hence compromising its authenticity and reproducibility whereas originality has often been the matter of least concern in most of such institutes.

Technology Advancement and its Global Impact

With advancement of technology, globally we have more version of publishing scientific work e.g. preprints, blogs open access journals and so on whereas in many developing countries including a few advanced ones, we are still adhered to obsolete practices, very likely merely because it serves the individuals more than investigating the scientific queries and serving the respective national interest hence generally in developing countries culturally the poorly developed infra-structure of institutes operates to give poor quality training rather than transforming research candidates into a competent members of Global Community of respective professions. Under prevailing situation it UTMOST need of time to review RESPECTIVE NATIONAL POLICY on HIGHER EDUCATION GLOBALLY particularly in AREA of SCIENCE with more emphasis in developing countries and make research and teaching a Globally integrated professional activity by adhering to higher quality standard recognized and integrated globally while recognizing different version or formats of reporting as authentic mode of publishing for referring the work and to do needful to design well integrated policies for all related fields accordingly all over the Globe otherwise the impact of gap in knowledge would be reflected as an increased ongoing sufferings with enhanced miseries in lives of Global Community as it is so far mainly because Knowledge is a Global Asset with having freedom to its accessibility while justifiably acknowledging all concerned whereas learning is most liberal activity that is globally integrated with having no boundaries and no regionally and

religiously biased limitations within the approved guideline of globally accepted ethics of doing research and publishing the work.

Challenge of this Era

With the intrusion of IT gadgets in life, the pace of life has become faster so is the generation of data and its printing. So much so is being published these days that it is difficult to differentiate between fair and fake with having limited access to knowledge but with enhanced demand for meeting higher target of productivity in terms publications, patent registration and winning the grants for supporting the targeted research, hence left with lesser space, flexibility and time for out of box thinking and provision to use smart approaches with comparatively lesser technology dependency, all these are the pre requisite for revealing new horizon in knowledge particularly in area of Life Sciences. Extensive involvement of technology and statistical treatment particularly in area of Life Sciences have been so far proven as added source of error [1,3] whereas reporting most novel findings while justifiably acknowledging all concerned is the real challenge of this era.

One of the most novel finding of this ERA e.g. a stimuli that can be physical chemical or biochemical or a biological event can alter the impact of mutation causing the lacking of function of certain essential genes operational within the same network regulated at transcriptional level compensated by boosting the activity of comparatively weaker genes whereas, SOD1 which encodes for Sod1p (Cu-Zn Superoxide dismutases) that binds copper and zinc ions and destroys the free superoxide radicals and CTR1 which encodes for Ctr1p that has high affinity membrane copper transporter, both lie within the same pathway and are regulated at transcriptional level in copper concentration dependent manner [3,5,6] present in the research thesis entitled Phenotypic variation in stress resistance between individual cells in isogenic populations of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* supported by NIH(US) University of Nottingham, United Kingdom and University of Karachi, Pakistan submitted to University of Nottingham UK in 2007, the findings remained unreported until recently published papers [3,5,6,8,9,10] also acknowledged in a press release of research gate blog [11]. However several papers built upon the data present in the thesis is yet to be published. Whereas a few paper on allied fields related to this domain of knowledge recently have been published [12,13].

The rejection of focused papers on this work done by most of the highest impact factor journals were made very likely because of disagreement on content and authorships on submissions as the most reputed journals usually avoid accepting manuscripts causing conflict of interest among authors and having disputed authorship no matter how scientifically important novel or out of the box the submitted work for reporting was hence leaving minimal space for accommodating the most novel findings for reporting by renowned most respectable journals if there is any disagreement.

The only option left to report the most novel work is to submit as review paper to comparatively less popular journals

but even after having the papers published in them, the global authorities do not generally take the published work seriously to do the needful as the authenticity of such work stays doubtful for having not published in the Most Reputed Journals those are recognized by Research Councils of Respective Countries, hence causing no change in the gap in understanding of knowledge that is being published even in Most Reputed Journals whereas the progression of knowledge and future investigation planned to be done end up having serious flaws partly because given data was analyzed under the inadequate understanding of knowledge excluding the lesser popular journals reports etc. not recognized by research council and other authorities giving research guidelines in respective countries ending up in generating an increasing gap in understanding of domain of knowledge in given and allied fields leads to wrongly use of available technology with having progression of research in given and related fields in wrong direction adding to miseries to Global Community. The accumulative outcome of present practices is ongoing generation of huge content of data as an outcome of poorly planned investigation based on biased knowledge deprived of independently done critical analysis of previously published data. As already mentioned earlier learning is an extremely liberal practice based on impartial critical review of published up-to-date work whereas research is quest to reveal the unexplored horizon of knowledge hence originality authenticity and reproducibility do not only matter rather these are pre requisite of under taking any research project. Otherwise science would keep on adding to miseries in life of Global Community rather supporting them to spend happy healthy and comfortable life with having minimal aging and illnesses, the basic objective of progression of Knowledge in domain of science.

Conclusion

It is need of time to recognize the different mean mode and medium of reporting research and integrate them globally while JUSTIFIEDLY acknowledging ALL CONCERNED ONLY helpful to do needful to transform latest findings into academic content comprising literature e.g. text books guides etc. to disperse related knowledge to main domain of Knowledge and allied fields at every level and to design related integrated academic and business policies to cater the need of Global Community accordingly since science and technology these days

have become finance-dependent and its impact is being experienced in every walk of day-today life everywhere. There is UTMOST need to design globally well integrated policies to discourage the mal practices catering individual s greed for name fame authority and, being religiously and regionally biased, politically influenced power driven selection on accessibility and transmission of knowledge including its propagation and its translation into technology while unjustifiedly acknowledging the individuals and to support the practices of honesty and high morality with genuine recognition of competency in field of Higher Education and Research.

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